

VARIATIONAL AND FINITE ELEMENT METHODS FOR FRACTIONAL DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS

TULKIN MAMATOV

Department of Natural Sciences, Bukhara State Technical University, Uzbekistan

Abstract. This paper presents the results of the theoretical justification for applying the Bubnov–Galerkin and Ritz methods to obtain numerical solutions of equations containing fractional differential operators. The structure of the numerical solution is proposed, and an error estimate for the approximate solution is obtained in the energy space metric induced by the fractional differentiation operator.

Keywords: equation, method, solution, Bubnov–Galerkin method, Ritz method.

ВАРИАЦИОННЫЕ И КОНЕЧНО-ЭЛЕМЕНТНЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ДЛЯ ДРОБНО-ДИФФЕРЕНЦИАЛЬНЫХ УРАВНЕНИЙ

Аннотация. В данной работе представлены результаты теоретического обоснования применения методов Бубнова–Галёркина и Ритца для получения численных решений уравнений, содержащих дробно-дифференциальные операторы. Предложена структура численного решения, а также получена оценка погрешности приближённого решения в метрике энергетического пространства, индуцированного оператором дробного дифференцирования.

Ключевые слова: уравнение, метод, решение, метод Бубнова–Галёркина, метод Ритца, дробно-дифференциальный оператор, метод конечных элементов.

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in the field of fractional calculus. Fractional differential equations have attracted significant attention due to their wide applications in various fields of science and engineering. Many phenomena in fluid mechanics, viscoelasticity, chemistry, physics, finance, and other areas can be modeled using mathematical tools from fractional calculus theory.

Such problems are generally not solvable in closed form, which makes the development and application of approximate solution methods, along with their theoretical justification, highly relevant. Although several studies have recently proposed numerical methods for certain classes of fractional differential equations, the theoretical substantiation of these approximate methods for more general classes of problems remains an open question.

The objective of this study is to develop a computational scheme for obtaining numerical solutions to fractional differential equations. The paper proposes a generalized Bubnov–Galerkin and Ritz method for determining approximate solutions.

Consider the following equation:

$$Tu = f, \tag{1}$$

where T is an operator involving fractional differentiation operators D^α , defined for functions $u(x)$ on the interval $[0,1]$ as:

$$(D_{0+}^\alpha u)(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\alpha)} \frac{d^n}{dx^n} \int_0^x \frac{u(s)}{(x-s)^{\alpha-n+1}} ds, \tag{2}$$

where $n-1 < \alpha \leq n$. These are known as left-sided and right-sided Riemann–Liouville fractional derivatives of order α .

Here, u is the unknown function, and f is a given function in $L^2(0,1)$. The operator T is a linear, generally unbounded, and not necessarily positive-definite operator.

For sufficiently smooth functions, the operator T coincides with the Weyl fractional differentiation operator, acting as:

$$Tu = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda_k \hat{u}_k \varphi_k, \quad (3)$$

where \hat{u}_k are the Fourier coefficients of u .

The following properties hold for this operator:

Lemma 1. The operator T is positive – definite.

Lemma 2. The operator T is symmetric.

Using these properties, we introduce the scalar product and the corresponding norm:

$$(u, v) = (Tu, v),$$

which in explicit form is:

$$(u, v) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \lambda_k \hat{u}_k \hat{v}_k.$$

By completing $L^2(0, 1)$ with respect to this norm, we obtain an energy space H_T .

Multiplying the original equation (1) by an arbitrary function v and integrating yields:

$$(Tu, v) = (f, v). \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) defines the weak (generalized) formulation of the problem. A generalized solution to equation (1) is a function satisfying equation (4) for any function v from the same space.

According to the Bubnov–Galerkin method, a system of basis functions $\{\varphi_i\}$ is selected in the energy space H_T , and the approximate solution is sought as:

$$u_N(x) = \sum_{i=1}^N c_i \varphi_i(x) \quad (5)$$

where the unknown coefficients c_i are determined from the system:

$$(Tu_N, \varphi_j) = (f, \varphi_j), \quad j = \overline{1, N}. \quad (6)$$

Substituting (5) and utilizing the linearity of the inner products, this system reduces to a system of linear algebraic equations:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N c_i (T\varphi_i, \varphi_j) = (f, \varphi_j), \quad j = \overline{1, N}. \quad (7)$$

Theorem. If:

1. Equation (1) has a unique solution for a given right-hand side.
2. The bilinear form (Tu, u) is coercive and bounded.
3. The sequence of subspaces V_N , spanned by $\{\varphi_i\}$, is dense in H_T .

Then for any finite N , system (6) has a unique solution, and the approximate solution u_N converges to the exact solution u as $N \rightarrow \infty$ in the energy space metric, with the error estimate:

$$\|u - u_N\| \leq C(N),$$

where $C(N) \rightarrow 0$ as $N \rightarrow \infty$.

Let us consider the following problem:

$$Au = f, \quad (8)$$

The approximate solution to (8) will be sought using the Ritz method, where the basis functions are chosen as the eigenfunctions of operator A , defined on a domain $D(A)$ consisting of continuous functions on $[0, 1]$ with continuous derivatives up to second order, satisfying the boundary conditions $u(0) = u(1) = 0$.

The eigenvalues λ_n and corresponding eigenfunctions φ_n of the operator A are:

$$\lambda_n = (n\pi)^2, \quad \varphi_n(x) = \sin(n\pi x).$$

Then, the approximate solution is sought as:

$$u_N(x) = \sum_{i=1}^N c_i \sin(i\pi x), \tag{9}$$

with the coefficients determined by: $c_i = \frac{(f, \varphi_i)}{\lambda_i}$.

Numerical Example:

Consider equation (1) with $\alpha = 2,5$; $q = 1$:

$$(D_{0+}^{2,5} u)(x) + u(x) = f(x),$$

with $f(x) = -x^2 + 2x$.

It can be shown that the exact solution is:

$$u(x) = x^2(1-x)^2$$

Applying the Ritz method, the approximate solution is sought as a trigonometric polynomial (9), with the coefficients computed from:

$$c_i = \frac{(f, \varphi_i)}{\lambda_i}.$$

The approximate solutions for $N = 10, 15, 20$ were compared with the exact solution at discrete points, as shown in Tables 1–3. The differences between exact and approximate values were minor, and increasing N beyond 15 did not lead to significant improvements in accuracy, indicating convergence.

Table 1.

x_i	$u(x_i)$	$u_{10}(x_i)$
0	0	0
0.1	-0.112693	-0.109898
0.2	-0.216672	-0.201131
0.3	-0.303631	-0.269012
0.4	-0.366226	-0.310407
0.5	-0.398157	-0.324481
0.6	-0.394782	-0.310407
0.7	-0.353214	-0.269012
0.8	-0.272511	-0.201131
0.9	-0.153749	-0.109898
1.0	0	0

Table 2.

x_i	$u(x_i)$	$u_{15}(x_i)$
0	0	0
0.1	-0.112693	-0.109811
0.2	-0.216672	-0.201220
0.3	-0.303631	-0.268961
0.4	-0.366226	-0.310456
0.5	-0.398157	-0.324419
0.6	-0.394782	-0.310456

0.7	-0.353214	-0.268961
0.8	-0.272511	-0.201220
0.9	-0.153749	-0.109811
1.0	0	0

Table 3.

x_i	$u(x_i)$	$u_{20}(x_i)$
0	0	0
0.1	-0.112693	-0.109793
0.2	-0.216672	-0.201197
0.3	-0.303631	-0.268947
0.4	-0.366226	-0.310455
0.5	-0.398157	-0.324425
0.6	-0.394782	-0.310455
0.7	-0.353214	-0.268947
0.8	-0.272511	-0.201197
0.9	-0.153749	-0.109793
1.0	0	0

This study developed a numerical scheme based on the Bubnov–Galerkin and Ritz methods for solving fractional differential equations. The theoretical justification of the proposed approach was established through coercivity and convergence theorems. Numerical experiments confirmed the effectiveness and convergence of the method for fractional order differential problems, with satisfactory accuracy achieved for relatively small values of N .

REFERENCES

1. Mamatov T. “Fractional integration operators in mixed weighted generalized Hölder spaces of function of two variables defined by mixed modulus of continuity”, *Journal of Mathematical Methods in Engineering, Auctores Publishing*, vol.1(1), 2019, P. 1-16
2. Mamatov T. “Operators of Volterra convolution type in generalized Hölder spaces”, *Poincare Journal of Analysis and Applications*, vol. 7(2), 2020, p. 275-288
3. Mamatov T and Mustafiev N. “Operators of Volterra convolution type in weighted generalized Hölder space”, *Poincare Journal of Analysis and Applications*, vol. 10(1), 2023, p. 135-154
4. Mamatov T. “Mixed Fractional Integration In Mixed Weighted Generalized Hölder Spaces” *Case Studies Journal*, vol 7(6), (2018) , p.1-8.
5. Mamatov T. “On isomorphism implemented by mixed fractional integrals in Hölder spaces”, *International Journal of Development Research*, vol. 9(5), pp. 27720-27730, May 2019
6. Mamatov T. “The Isomorphism Realized By Mixed Fractional Integrals In Hölder Classes”, *Journal of Computer Science & Computational Mathematics*, vol. 10(2), June 2020, P. 35-40
7. Mamatov T. “Finite-element method for decisions the fractional differential equation”, International Scientific Conference on Modern Problems of Applied Science and Engineering AIP Conf. Proc. 3244, 020032-1–020032-9, 27.11.2024; <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0242238>
8. Mamatov T. “Representation of distribution functions by fractional Riemann-Liouville integrals”, International Scientific Conference on Modern Problems of Applied Science and Engineering AIP Conf. Proc. 3244, 020002-1–020002-10, 27.11.2024; <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0242239>
9. Marinov T.M., Ramirez N., Santamaria F. “Fractional Integration toolbox”, *Fractional Calculus and Applied Analysis*, 2013. vol. 16, no 3. pp. 670 – 681.
10. Zhu L., Fan Q. “Numerical solution of nonlinear fractional-order Volterra integro-differential equations by SCW”, *Commun Nonlinear Sci Numer Simulat*, 2013. no 18. pp. 1203-1213.
11. Mamatov T. “Kasr tartibli differensial tenglamalarni chekli elementlar usuli asosida sonli yechish”, *Международный научный журнал «In the World of Science and Education»*, 15 aprel, 2026. 3-10 bet. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19786778>